

Exploring the Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) Support in Assisting Students' English-Speaking Skills

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) support in helping students' English-speaking skills. With the increasing importance of speaking skills in academic, professional and social contexts, this research aims to analyze the role of AI assistance in helping students' English-speaking skills. This research uses descriptive qualitative methods with 4 sixth semester student participants from a private university in Purwokerto who often use AI to help their English-speaking skills. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews and analyzed using data reduction techniques, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. The research results show that AI makes a significant contribution to English language learning through personalization of learning, automatic evaluation. However, there are challenges in using AI such as lack of human interaction, limited features and AI not being able to understand complex situations. This research provides insight into the benefits and challenges of using AI in language learning, as well as its implications for the development of students' English-speaking skills.

1. Introduction

English Speaking Skill, occupies a central position in academic, professional, and social contexts. In this era of globalization, English speaking skills are not only an additional skill, but also a major key to success in various fields. In the academic context, English speaking skills help effective communication between students, educators, and researchers from diverse linguistic backgrounds. This is reinforced by the opinion of Bestari et al. (2024) who state that one of important and essential skill in English is speaking. Speaking is an important part of second language learning and teaching. The purpose of speaking is to convey ideas to the person we are talking to about what we want to convey. In a conversation, speaking is one of the components. So, speaking here is a way of expressing or expressing an opinion or a word that you want to express. In the professional world, English is the global language of business, giving it an edge in international negotiations and collaboration. In the social context, English plays an important role in facilitating cross-cultural interactions and building relationships globally. Therefore, it is important to

understand and address the challenges that students often face in developing their English-speaking skills to ensure their success in various domains of life.

Students face various challenges in developing and improving their English language skills. These include difficulties in creating a suitable environment for practicing, lack of ideas and vocabulary, lack of confidence, and fear of making mistakes. Other challenges include difficulty in pronunciation and grammar issues. To overcome these challenges, students can read a lot of literature in English, observe, write, practice speaking, by utilizing various other learning media on the internet such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) to maximize their English-speaking learning process.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the education sector offers promising opportunities to overcome long-standing challenges and create new possibilities for student engagement and success. This is in line with the opinion of (Tjahyanti, 2022) who states that in this competitive era, there are more innovations, especially in the field of education, many teaching and learning activities involve AI to improve the quality of learning. Some of the key areas where AI is being applied include: Personalized Learning, namely in the field of education, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has brought about a paradigm shift and paved the way for personalized learning experiences that meet individual needs, learning styles and preferences of students (Rane et al, 2023). Here are some examples of AI that students can use to practice their English speaking, including Duolingo, DeepL, Google Translate, Chat GPT, Elsa Speaks, and Gemini.

Apart from education, AI also extends to various fields such as health, transportation, finance, manufacturing, and security. Apart from its benefits, however, AI also has a negative impact, namely the potential for excessive dependence, for example in using GPT Chat to brainstorm ideas for English speaking, students will tend to rely on AI rather than their ideas. Meanwhile in Indonesia, the use of AI such as Chat GPT is very wide to exploit its potential, especially in the world of education, but this needs to be watched out for because it is necessary to formulate academic regulations for the application of AI in the academic environment (Sasa, 2023).

This research has at least three gaps from previous studies. First, the participants in this research were English language education students from a 6th-semester private religious-based university. In previous research, they used participants from universities (Xiao & Zhi, 2023; Zhou, 2023; Wagan, 2023) Second, the current research focuses on the Supportive Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Helping Students' English Language Skills. On the other hand, previous studies focused on the extent to which ChatGPT helps students to complete language learning tasks (Xiao & Zhi, 2023), second focused on students' perceptions of various interactive activities when practicing speaking skills with AI applications (Zhou, 2023), third focused on AI-based augmented game learning (Wagan, 2023). Lastly, their research uses indicators from certain theoretical reviews (Xiao & Zhi, 2023; Zhou, 2023; Wagan, 2023), while this research uses indicators created by Xiao & Zhi (2023) and Zhou (2023).

Through the brief explanation in the previous paragraph, this research aims to: 1) explore the role of AI in assisting English speaking skills: Analyze how the role of AI technology can be used as a tool in assisting students' English-speaking skills. 2) Exploring AI Tools: Examine various AI applications and technologies such as Google Translate, Duolingo,

Grammarly, or other AI-based applications that might be used by students in assisting English speaking skills. 3) Investigating the challenges of using AI: Identifying the challenges of using AI as a tool that students use to help with English speaking skills. To achieve these objectives, the researchers formulated the research questions: "How does the role of AI assistance assist students' English-speaking skills?"

2. Literature Review

2.1. Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a field of computer science that focuses on developing systems capable of performing tasks that normally require human intelligence. These tasks include recognizing speech, understanding natural language, understanding visual information, making decisions, and learning from experience. This concept is in line with the perspective of Tang (2024) who defines AI as the ability of computers or robots to carry out tasks that usually require human intelligence. Tang emphasized that AI systems are designed to mimic cognitive processes, including learning, reasoning, problem-solving and language use. For example, AI-based educational tools can interact with students in real time, offering personalized feedback and adaptive learning experiences that meet individual needs. Apart from that, AI has a close relationship with learning technology, this is because technology has a special role in the progress of the world of learning. This is in line with An-Nisa et al. (2023) who state that technology has an important role in the educational context, especially in learning English.

2.2. The Role of AI in Education

Adaptive Learning. AI can be used to create adaptive learning systems, namely learning systems that adjust the content, level of difficulty, and teaching methods to suit individual student needs. With continuous data analysis, AI can identify students' weaknesses and strengths and provide learning recommendations that suit their conditions. The use of artificial intelligence to enhance adaptive learning provides excellent feedback to students. Through artificial intelligence, schools use applications or media that can automate tasks such as providing advice, selecting appropriate teaching materials, or adapting the curriculum to student needs (Dhaniswara, 2023).

Personalized Learning. Today, AI enables personalized learning by providing learning experiences tailored to each student's unique learning style, interests, and needs. This can help improve student engagement and their learning outcomes. This is in line with Rane et al, (2023) who stated that in the field of education, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has brought about a paradigm shift and paved the way for personalized learning experiences that meet individual needs, learning styles, and student preferences.

Game-Based Learning Wagan et al. (2023) states that game-based learning is considered an active learning approach where games are designed to increase students' intelligence (IQ level). This learning technique encourages critical thinking and improves problem-solving skills. Therefore, the development of AI-based applications and games can make language learning a more interesting and interactive experience. These games can be designed to improve speaking skills while maintaining student levels of enjoyment and engagement.

Automatic Evaluation. AI can automatically evaluate student work, such as multiple-choice exams, writing assignments, or even creative projects. The use of AI in assessments provides benefits such as objectivity, efficiency, consistency, analytical capabilities, development of assessment programs, personalization, flexibility, and reducing fraud in assessments (Supianto, 2023).

Virtual Tutor. The AI tutor system can aid students in understanding lesson material, provide additional explanations, and provide exercises appropriate to the student's level of understanding. This is confirmed by research conducted by Chen et al. (2021) who found that students who interacted with virtual tutors and chatbots showed significant improvements in speaking ability, fluency, and confidence in using English.

The function of AI in English-speaking classes is to optimize the user's way of learning so that the learning process can be better and more effective. AI will optimize the way users learn, as has been implemented by platforms such as Duolingo, Ruang Guru, and others. In addition, AI can also use information collected by digital education tools to gain a deeper understanding. With educational technology that utilizes AI, students can carry out teaching and learning activities using Chat GPT, Google Translate, and Google Classroom. The above studies provide a clearer understanding of the role of AI in language learning, showing the potential of AI to improve language acquisition. By utilizing AI technology to help English language skills can be transformed into a more interactive, adaptive, and interesting experience for students.

2.3. The Challenges of Using AI in Language Learning

Lack of human interaction. The absence of human interaction is the primary drawback of AI as a language learning aid (Khanzode & Sarode 2020). While some resources allow users to practice live conversations with tutors or native speakers, the majority of learning activities are self-paced and do not require face-to-face communication. For students that would rather have a more individualized and engaged learning experience, this could be an issue.

The next challenge is the integration of AI in education lies in privacy issues. When AI systems collect and analyze large amounts of student data, including performance metrics, learning patterns, and behavioral data, the potential for privacy violations becomes a significant issue. Safeguarding sensitive information is critical to maintaining trust within the educational community. Striking a balance between leveraging AI for personalized learning and protecting individual privacy requires strong data protection measures, secure storage protocols, and transparent communication about data use policies (Butt, et. al., 2022, Khosravi, et. al., 2022, Malhotra, et al., 2021 as cited in Ayeni, et al., 2024).

Another difficult element in this situation is balance. striking a balance between valuing creativity and making sure AI is used responsibly in the classroom. Even if artificial intelligence (AI) presents therefore unseen possibilities for learning and enhancing academic results, caution is required to avoid unfavorable consequences. Collaboration between educational institutions, technology developers, regulatory organizations, and the government is necessary to construct a framework that protects against potential risks and fosters innovation in order to achieve the goal of striking this balance. Thus, continuous oversight, open communication, and a dedication to resolving new ethical concerns are necessary for the responsible use of AI (Leslie, 2020, Miao, et al., 2021).

In conclusion, the use of AI in language learning offers innovative solutions to existing challenges. In using AI in effective and efficient language learning, it is necessary to pay attention to aspects of ethics, security, and data privacy and must adapt to students' conditions

2.4. The Importance of Speaking Skill

Good communication. Good speaking skills will enable a person to convey thoughts, ideas and information clearly and effectively to others. This ability is essential in communicating effectively in a variety of situations, both within and outside a professional context. M Stewart L. Tubbs and Sylvania Moss in the book *Human Communication* (1996) state that effective communication is characterized by understanding, can cause pleasure, influence attitudes, improve good social relations, and ultimately lead to action.

Success in Career. Good speaking skills are one of the keys to success in a career. The ability to speak confidently and effectively can help someone in public presentations, negotiations, job interviews, and various other professional situations. In line with Communication skills which are important skills to learn so you can communicate smoothly. Both with superiors and with subordinates and office colleagues (Oussi, 2017).

Improved Social Relations. As social creatures, humans will always interact with each other to continue their lives (Hasanah, 2021). Good speaking skills can help build and maintain good social relationships. People who can communicate well tend to find it easier to build strong relationships with other people, whether in personal, professional, or social settings.

Leadership. Good speaking skills are one of the essential characteristics of an effective leader. A leader who can speak clearly, convince, and inspire others will be more effective in leading a team or organization. Speaking skills can also make someone a leader because public speaking is oral communication about a topic in front of people that aims to influence, educate, explain and inform others so that they are interested in what we say (Sumrahadi et al., 2019).

In conclusion, based on the brief explanation of the importance of speaking skills, it is imperative for individuals to develop their speaking skills, either through active practice, learning from experience, or seeking help from a coach or mentor.

3. Research Methodology

In this study, the research method used by researchers is descriptive qualitative. Furidha (2023) states that descriptive qualitative research has the characteristics of a systematic, accurate, and factual description of the facts, properties, and relationships between the phenomena being studied. This method can provide an in-depth description of a person's opinion in interacting with the object under study. The researcher wants to explore students' opinions about the Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) Support in Assisting Students' English-speaking skills.

3.1. Participants

The study involved four sixth-semester English Language Education students from a private university in Purwokerto. Bartholomew et al, (2021) state that the ideal sample size for interviews is four to ten, but for student projects can have as many as three to six participants. Although the number of participants may seem limited, it can provide the

researcher with useful insights and viewpoints from participants who fulfil the criteria. The researcher employed a purposive sampling technique, targeting students who frequently utilize AI to enhance their English-language communication skills. Those who met the researcher's criteria were categorized as potential participants and selected in accordance with the researcher's requirements for this study. Before conducting purposive sampling, researchers conducted a survey by distributing questionnaires. By using a questionnaire, information that can be measured in the form of attitudes, perceptions, motivations, and reactions will be obtained (Suwartono, 2014). Therefore, the purpose of the survey was to find participants who really engaged with AI in practicing their English-speaking skills.

3.2. Instruments

The researcher used semi-structured interviews as a data collection technique. From the interviews, the researcher can easily get in-depth information about students' opinions on the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) support in assisting English speaking skills. In creating interview questions, the researcher referred to the theoretical review from Zou et al., (2023) and Xiao & Zhi (2023). Interviews were conducted face-to-face or virtually using Zoom meetings or voice notes, depending on the situation at the time of data collection. There were several steps taken in this research: 1) the researcher prepared an interview guide and a recording device on a smartphone, 2) the researcher determined the place and time of the interview with the participant, 3) the researcher asked questions to the participant based on the interview guide, 4) the researcher recorded the conversation during the interview, 5) the researcher analyzed and transcribed the interview.

Table 1: Interview Guide

NO	ASPECTS	INDICATOR	ITEM
1	AI Tools	Students' experiences and comprehension of the role of AI in helping their English language skills	1,2,3
2	Form of Interaction	Form student interaction with AI to practice speaking English	4
3	Challenges	Students' awareness of the challenges and weaknesses associated with using AI to help their English speaking.	5, 6, 7

3.3. Data Analysis Procedures

The data in this study was analyzed using three activities: 1) Data Reduction 2) Drawing or verifying conclusions (Sugiyono, 2015). The data were categorized into several points (understanding of AI, perceived improvement, forms of interaction with AI, challenges in using AI, and Recommendations for AI users). The explanation of the three steps is as follows: 1) Data reduction is the process of selecting data from field notes or transcriptions to be focused, simplified, separated, and transformed. The researcher transcribed the information collected from the interviews. In this process, the researcher followed a series of steps to transcribe the data. Initially, the researcher listened to the interview recordings. Then, the researcher transcribed the answers using Microsoft Word. 2) Data Display, at this stage, the researcher presents the interview transcripts in tabular form with questions and

conducts analysis. For the next transcript, the researcher presents it in summary form with the answers given. 3) Drawing or verifying conclusions, at the final stage, the researcher summarizes the overall opinion of all interviewees. The results will be summarized as how the Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) Support in Helping Students' English-Speaking Skills.

4. Findings

4.1. AI Tools Used

Participant 1 (P1) used SiVi AI to train his speaking skills, he mentioned that the features provided by SiVi AI provide direct correction if there are pronunciation errors that are not in accordance with the given sentence then the sentence will be colored red.

"I use AI to train my speaking skills for the AI that I use, SiVi. I use the AI to improve my speaking skills and to train my pronunciation, so if we make a wrong pronunciation, the wrong word is highlighted and we are told to revise the sentence in the text." (P1)

Participant 2 (P2) uses Duolingo and Chat GPT to prepare for English speaking classes and daily practice to familiarize English in his daily life.

"I use AI to practice my English skills, this experience also includes preparing for English speaking classes and practicing English in my daily life. Examples of AIs I've used include Duolingo and GPT chat for more complex conversations." (P2)

Then participant 3 (P3) used AI such as Chat GPT, Gemini, Google Translate focusing on training and increasing his vocabulary.

"I use AI to train my vocabulary skills, I use AI generally as commonly used by other people such as GPT chat, Gemini, Google Translate also includes AI and sometimes uses Perplexity for alternative Chat GPT, then sometimes for paraphrasing exercises I usually use Quilbot, for example for Google Translate and DeepL I use 2 it can be called 2 comparisons of English and Indonesian compared well that can help me choose the right vocabulary or word order for my English." (P3)

Then Participant 4 (P4) used AI to practice his English-speaking skills and also to hone his writing skills.

"I use AI in practicing my English-speaking skills, when I was in the 4th semester I used AI to brainstorm when I was going to speak, besides that I also used AI for Essay writing course, and I used to be required to use Chat GPT to brainstorm ideas that we would write and also last semester I used it to analyze articles." (P4)

4.2. Improved Language Skills

Participant 1 (P1) said that with the help of AI his English-speaking ability has improved, especially in the parts of pronunciation, vocabulary and grammar.

"AI has greatly improved my speaking skills in terms of pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar." (P1)

Participant 2 (P2) revealed that practicing speaking English using AI helped his English skills especially in the aspects of frequency, vocabulary and grammar. He also stated that because he often interacts with Chat GPT which gives natural responses and can provide corrections and Duolingo which can increase new vocabulary and vary his poor English in

terms of pronunciation, vocabulary and messy grammar to become clearer and more structured.

"Practicing speaking using AI can help improve my English skills, especially my frequency, vocabulary and grammar, and this improvement also occurs because I often practice conversations with GPT chat which gives natural responses and corrects my mistakes and duo lingo can also increase my new vocabulary, like, new and varied vocabulary. Before the use of AI, my English was bad from speech, vocabulary pronunciation and grammar was also messy and after using AI features such as Duolingo, Chat GPT also it was more like my speech was clearer and pronunciation was also correct and the sentences spoken were also structured." (P2)

Participant 3 (P3) informed that because of using AI he felt an improvement in his English-speaking skills, especially in the vocabulary aspect.

"Because from the previous point, I practiced more vocabulary, of course what I feel is that my vocabulary has increased, so from using AI platforms, I got a lot of new vocabulary." (P3)

Participant 4 (P4) stated that while using AIs such as Deepl and Chat GPT, he felt an improvement in his English-speaking ability. In the vocabulary section, there is an increase in new vocabulary and in the pronunciation and fluency section, there is also an improvement from not knowing before to knowing how to pronounce it.

"Of course, it can improve English language skills to find information in English to improve English language skills including the vocabulary part For the fluency part of vocabulary pronunciations thank God, I got new words that initially did not know the pronunciation so I know and there are some that I used to pronounce like this but I pronounce it correctly like this as long as I use Deepl and Chat GPT." (P4)

4.3. Interaction Preferences

Participant 1 (P1) prefers to interact with AI through text, because writing information through text is very valid or clear.

"I prefer to interact with the AI for text, because text is very valid information and there are already references from sources and trusted, maybe I am more inclined to text." (P1)

Participant 2 (P2) often interacts with AI directly through voice because it feels more interactive than reading text, but sometimes he also combines voice or direct with text depending on the need.

"I prefer direct voice, because I get more interaction, compared to text which is just reading without interaction, but sometimes I combine the two depending on my own needs." (P2)

Participant 3 (P3) stated that in interacting with AI, sometimes combining direct (voice) and textual, but participant 3 tends to use text more often in their interactions because they have not found an AI with a good vocal level.

"Sometimes I also practice both vocals, but for vocal training I am limited to finding which AI has a good vocal level, I often interact using text so I command by texting something." (P3)

Participant 4 (P4) used more text in interacting with the AI, and also informed that her interaction started with looking up rich words first on how to pronounce them, then practicing the pronunciation, if it sounded good or feasible, then looking for AI applications to practice her English skills.

"For that I prefer to use text, so we look for words first that we want to say, then we practice first how to say it, if it sounds good or feasible maybe I will just look for ways to say it through the AI application, so practice first for pronunciation, not immediately looking like that." (P4)

4.4. Challenges

Participant 1's (P1) challenge when using AI lies more in the interaction limitations. AI has limitations in interaction where it cannot understand the meaning or humor of what is being said, next is context limitations, so AI can have limitations in understanding context and complex situations so it is very difficult to understand deeper meaning.

"So, the challenge I face for using AI is more about the limitations of interaction. AI has limitations in interaction, AI can't understand the meaning that we say or the humor that we say, and then from the second, the limitations of context, so AI can have limitations in understanding context and complex situations, so it is very difficult to understand the deeper meaning of the conversation." (P1)

Participant 2 (P2) experienced challenges or obstacles when using AI as a tool to help him with his English language skills. The response given by the AI was inconsistent with what was desired, so it had to be really careful when giving commands.

"The challenge is the lack of response that matches what we want, so we have to be clear in giving orders, to overcome this I try to communicate with native speakers." (P2)

Participant 3 (P3) informed that with a limited and rigid AI system, the interactions that occur with AI are limited, in which case AI becomes less flexible.

"There are definitely challenges, the name is also AI by system, so it's like limited, rigid, so it's not as flexible as we learn with people, it's more about the rigidity, and more about the limited features." (P3)

Participant 4 (P4) said that the disadvantages he experienced were limitations when using AI such as in DeepL which has features that are limited by paid subscriptions because the limit of using AI is 1500 words per day, then in AI Chat GPT has the disadvantage that often the information provided is too general so that it requires further checking and accuracy for effectiveness in training English speaking skills.

"Of course, there are weaknesses that I have experienced so far, perhaps using AI like DeepL, there are several features that are limited by subscriptions that we have to pay for if our translation results are more than 1,500 words per day, and media tools such as Chat GPT as I explained "Previously, the results from GPT chat were often too general, so we had to cross-check, maybe that was the weakness." (P4)

5. Discussion

In the context of AI tools used, all participants stated that they use AI to help their English-speaking skills, there are a variety of AIs that participants use, including: SiVi which was used to practice speaking and pronunciation, Duolingo and Gemini provided features for speaking, listening, and vocabulary, Chat GPT and Perplexity were used for more complex conversations and brainstorming, Google Translate, Grammarly and DeepL were used for translation and comparing vocabulary, and Quilbot for paraphrasing.

SiVi AI provides immediate correction of pronunciation errors. This is in accordance with the concept of AI as Automatic Evaluation proposed by Supianto (2023) which states that the use of AI in assessment provides benefits such as objectivity, efficiency, consistency, analytical capabilities, assessment program development, personalization, flexibility, and reducing fraud in assessment. Furthermore, Fitria et al. (2023) also stated that Duolingo can help aspects of speaking skills which include pronunciation, fluency, and grammar. From the explanation of several concepts above, it shows that these AI tools can be said to be effective in helping users' English-speaking skills.

In the context of Improved English-speaking skills, all participants reported improvements in various aspects of English language skills, including pronunciation: AI helped participants improve the pronunciation of difficult words. Vocabulary: The use of AI increased the amount of vocabulary that participants mastered. Grammar: AI provided feedback that helped participants improve their sentence structure. This is in accordance with the theoretical concepts from Haddadian & Haddadian (2024) showing that feedback from Grammarly significantly improved students' speaking ability.

In the context of interaction preferences, it can be said that most participants preferred interacting with the AI through text, although some also preferred interacting through voice or by combining both text and voice. These preferences vary depending on the needs of the individual, suggesting that AI can customize the way it interacts with users, for example through the use of more formal or informal language, written or voice interaction, and a combination of written and voice. This is in accordance with the concept of AI can be personalized learning stated by Rane et al, (2023) that, with the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the field of education can bring a paradigm shift and pave the way for personalized learning experiences to meet individual needs, learning styles, and student preferences.

In the context of challenges, all participants expressed challenges when using AI, including: Interaction Limitations: AI cannot understand the nuances of conversation, humor, or complex context, limited responses: Sometimes, AI responses do not match user expectations, requiring further clarification, and limitations features: Some apps have limitations that affect the learning experience, such as word limits in translations. This is due to the lack of human interaction with AI. Khanzode & Sarode, (2020) stated that the weakness of AI as a language learning aid is the absence of human interaction. And in this case AI also cannot handle complex situations therefore AI will not be as perfect or replace humans. This is in line with De Cremer & Kasparov, (2021) who state that when compared to AI which is only responsive to available data, human capabilities are broader, humans have the ability to imagine, anticipate, feel and assess changing situations, which makes it possible them to shift from short-term to long-term concerns.

This is also supported by the opinion expressed by Hasanah (2021) that to continue life as social creatures, humans will always form interactions with each other. Human interactions provide opportunities to develop social skills, understand non-verbal cues, and adapt to a variety of communication styles that AI technology cannot fully replicate. Therefore, although AI makes a significant contribution to the learning process, participants emphasized that learning experiences involving human interaction remain an irreplaceable component in achieving true English fluency.

In the context of recommendations for AI users, this is the advice given by all participants to students who want to use AI to help their English speaking skills: Using a Combination of AI Tools: It is recommended to utilize various AI tools such as Duolingo and Chat GPT for a more comprehensive learning experience, Interacting with Speakers Native: While AI is useful, interaction with native speakers is still important to understand language and cultural nuances, Interesting Uses of AI Apps: Apps like Duolingo and Quizlet that have elements of gamification can make the learning process more fun. By utilizing gamification in AI to help students' English-speaking skills, the learning process becomes more interesting, efficient, and effective, which ultimately helps students achieve higher language competence. This can be connected with the concept of Game-Based Learning which is considered an active learning approach where the aim of game-based learning is designed to increase student intelligence (Wagan et al, 2023).

6. Conclusion

This research concludes that the use of AI can play a role in helping students' English-speaking skills effectively. The AI tools used by participants, such as SiVi, Duolingo, Chat GPT, and others, have helped with various aspects of language proficiency, including pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar. The participants reported significant improvements in their speaking abilities, especially in terms of pronunciation, vocabulary and grammar. Additionally, participants preferred interacting with AI through text-based interactions, although some participants also preferred or combined text and voice interactions. Challenges faced by participants included AI's limitations in understanding nuance, humor, and complex contexts, as well as certain AI tools' limitations in providing accurate responses or having limited features. Even though there are several challenges and limitations, AI tools still make a significant contribution to the language learning process, especially English through personalized learning, automatic evaluation. However, human interaction remains essential to understanding the complex nuances of language and culture. For readers in this case are students, teachers and AI tool developers are expected to consider these findings to improve tools to help English speaking skills and support so that we can all achieve higher English language competence.

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